

KIDNER – A WORLDWIDE DECENTRALISED MATCHING SYSTEM FOR KIDNEY TRANSPLANTS

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Abstract

Individuals suffering from kidney failure today face significant challenges in order to obtain a transplant. They are placed on a waiting list and ranked by priority in hope that a kidney from a deceased donor is a transplant match. They do have another option: a living donor; someone they know, family or friend, willing to give them a kidney. These people may not be a transplant match, however there is a solution, a “Kidney Exchange” or a “Kidney Paired Donation”. In these programs, if two mismatched pairs (living donor and kidney recipient) can be grouped together so that they become transplant matches, both kidney failure patients can receive a kidney. While a great solution, these programs have a significant pitfall. They are limited to the specific registry regions participating in their program. The Kidner project was developed to help these exchange programs better detect life-saving opportunities and enable more people to access kidney transplants.

Keywords:

1. Introduction

The average waiting time for a kidney transplant in the US is 3 to 5 years,¹ during this time patients have to go through an onerous process of dialysis at least 3 times a week, negatively impacting their normal social and work life balance. Being on dialysis is expensive, about US\$60 billion is spent in the US each year on kidney healthcare - 28% of Medicare’s budget,² and transplants are overall much cheaper than ongoing dialysis. Illness may worsen while waiting for a transplant and in the worst case, patients may die.

There is another option: a living donor; someone they know, family or friend who is willing to give them a kidney. Unfortunately many factors like blood type and HLAs need to be the same and these people may not be a transplant match. To solve this “Kidney Exchange Programs” or “Kidney Paired Donation programs” (KPD), have been created.³ In these programs two mismatched pairs (living donor and kidney recipient) can be grouped together so that they become appropriate transplant matches and both kidney failure patients can receive a kidney. Currently, KPD accounts for 10% of live kidney transplants in the United States. The pool of participants in KPDs face the same constraints as Traditional Cadaveric Kidney Transplant lists, they are limited to a specific country or region.

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2. Aim

Our goal is to make the current transplant system more efficient and more secure. To do so we realised that we need to increase the data volume by involving more hospitals in the process and asking them to share their data to create a bigger and more relevant pool. Such an effort requires us to address governance and trust among systems, as well as offer transparency for all actors in the system. A blockchain architecture was considered to be the best way to create a multi-parties ecosystem of hospitals and healthcare actors that want to achieve a common goal: better and safer care for the patients.

3. Material and methods

A patient centric view of the process is described. There are two prerequisites, i) the hospital is a safe place where healthcare professionals can help the patients and provide a guarantee that there is not pressure or on going traffic into the kidney donation process, and ii) the hospital information system is secured, the database can't be breached by an attacker to steal patients data and the network is private so that no one else can listen or interfere with the internal network and critical data that are transmitted and stored.

Donor, patient and doctor meet at the doctor's office. They are connected through the doctor's computer on the hospital private network with direct access to the hospital database which is secured as per prerequisite (ii). Information about the donor and recipient are filled automatically from the file or by the doctor. They then individually sign a certificate that states 3 things:

the donor is willing to give a kidney the recipient is willing to accept the kidney and the doctor agreed that recipient's health is good, that it is safe for him or her to have a transplant, and that the same assessment pertains the donor's health.

The doctor and the patient sign this form with a private key (multi-signature scheme), triggering the certificate to be anonymised, encrypted locally, and sent to the blockchain via an internet connection.

4. Results

A public opensource blockchain called Ethereum was used to illustrate the Kidner concept and the patient journey in a simple way. The front end and blockchain smart contracts described below were developed by the hackathon team of Chainhack 2015. For the proof of concept the Ethereum platform was used to implement a basic matching system through a smart contract.

5. Conclusions

Kidner is a collaborative project that was developed to address the financial and security challenges that face cross border transplantation. It aims at creating a KPD programme that extends the mismatched live donor-recipient pool through a decentralised non-profit system deployed world-wide to improve patient care and outcomes, making possible analysis

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and matching of patients while providing complete anonymity. It is envisaged that this system will lead to the first Kidner-based surgeries, enabling increased renal transplants per year.

6. Keywords

Transplant; kidney; privacy; security; blockchain.

Author biography

Sajida ZOUARHI Sajida Zouarhi is an engineer and a PhD student in Computer Science and Network with Orange labs and LIG (computer science laboratory of Grenoble). Her research work is about Blockchain-based solutions and “Quality of service of complex and heterogeneous systems for critical data transmission” especially in Healthcare and Internet of Things. She has co-founded the Kidner Project in 2015 and is now working at ConsenSys as a blockchain architect.